

Plots of L.H.S. of equation (10) against μ at all the temperatures were linear, the intercepts of which at $\mu=0$ gave $\log K_1$ and the slopes gave β_1 . The values of pK_1 thus found have been recorded in Table 2.

It will be seen that the values of pK_1 and pK_2 obtained with different series at all the temperatures closely agree among themselves and with the values reported by the original workers. Only at 298.15 K the difference in pK_1 goes upto 0.006 and that in pK_2 upto 0.007. The linear plots and the constancy of β_1 and β_2 for different series of solutions confirm the assumption that β_1 and β_2 are independent of the composition of ionic atmosphere.

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Mechanism of Ruthenium(III) Catalysed Oxidation of 4-Aminobutyric Acid by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III) Ions

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USE of catalytic amount of ruthenium(III) chloride^{1,2} prompted us to investigate the kinetics and mechanism of ruthenium(III) catalysed oxidation of 4-aminobutyric acid by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) ions. The results show zero-order dependence on [hexacyanoferrate(III)] and first-order on both [Ru(III)] and [OH⁻]. First order dependence on lower [4-aminobutyric acid] tends to zero-order at higher concentrations. A suitable

mechanism involving formation of a transient complex between Ru(III) and substrate has been proposed.

Experimental

The solution of ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson Matthey) was prepared by dissolving the sample in hydrochloric acid of known strength. All other reagents used were of AR grade except 4-aminobutyric acid (Fluka), sodium perchlorate (Riedel) and ferroin indicator (E. Merck).

The reaction was followed by quenching the reaction mixture in H₂SO₄ and estimating the ferrocyanide formed volumetrically against standard ceric sulphate solution.

Results and Discussion

Variation of hexacyanoferrate(III) concentration shows zero-order dependence on [hexacyanoferrate(III)]. The rate of oxidation follows first-order kinetics with respect to [4-aminobutyric acid] at lower concentrations of 4-ABA and tends to zero-order at higher concentrations. The reaction rate is directly proportional to the [ruthenium(III) chloride] showing first-order dependence on [Ru(III)]. The reaction rate increases with increasing [OH⁻] and is also first-order in [OH⁻].

The reactions were carried out in the temperature range 25-45° (Table 1) and the value of ΔE^\ddagger calculated from the Arrhenius plot is 18.4 ± 0.2 k cal mole⁻¹. Positive effect of ionic strength of the medium on reaction rate was observed.

It is well known that amino acids exist as zwitter ions in aqueous solution and dissociate to amino acid anions. The pK values for

systems are reported³ to be ~ 9.60 (at 25°). Since the pH of the reaction mixture is >10, the anion of 4-aminobutyric acid is assumed to be the reactive species. Ruthenium(III) chloride exists as [Ru(H₂O)₆]³⁺ in dilute hydrochloric acid⁴. Such type of aquo-complexes are known to exist in the form [Ru(H₂O)₆OH]²⁺ in equilibrium⁵ with hexa-aquo form.

In alkaline medium, the dissociation (1) would be highly favoured, suggesting that [Ru(H₂O)₅-x(OH)_x]^{3-x} is the real reactive species of ruthenium(III) chloride in alkaline medium.

On the basis of the above facts the following scheme of oxidation is proposed where S stands for 4-aminobutyric acid and Ru(III) has been written in place of the reactive species of ruthenium(III) chloride for the sake of simplicity.

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TABLE I—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF [REACTANTS] ON REACTION RATE AT 35°

(a=25°, b=30°, c=40° and d=45°)

[K ₂ Fe(ON) ₆] × 10 ³ M	[4-ABA] × 10 ³ M	[Ru(III)] × 10 ³ M	[NaOH] × 10 ³ M	(-dc/dt) × 10 ³ mole lit ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
1.00	1.00	1.91	1.00	1.54
1.25	1.00	1.91	1.00	1.60
1.43	1.00	1.91	1.00	1.45
1.67	1.00	1.91	1.00	1.47
2.00	1.00	1.91	1.00	1.50
2.50	1.00	1.91	1.00	1.40
1.25	0.40	1.91	1.00	4.00*
1.25	0.50	1.91	1.00	5.05*
1.25	0.67	1.91	1.00	5.66*
1.25	1.00	1.91	1.00	6.00*
1.25	1.43	1.91	1.00	6.04*
1.25	2.00	1.91	1.00	5.60*
1.25	1.00	0.76	1.00	1.60
1.25	1.00	1.58	1.00	3.00
1.25	1.00	2.29	1.00	4.90
1.25	1.00	2.67	1.00	5.20
1.25	1.00	3.06	1.00	6.25
1.25	1.00	3.82	1.00	7.10
1.25	0.67	1.91	0.50	4.00**
1.25	0.67	1.91	0.66	5.02**
1.25	0.67	1.91	1.00	8.60**
1.25	0.67	1.91	1.35	12.46**
1.25	0.67	1.91	1.66	14.40**
1.25	0.67	1.91	2.00	17.96**
1.25	1.00	1.91	1.00	0.74 ^a
1.25	1.00	1.91	1.00	1.07 ^b
1.25	1.00	1.91	1.00	2.80 ^c
1.25	1.00	1.91	1.00	4.17 ^d

[4-ABA]=[4-Aminobutyric acid], μ=0.2M, *μ=0.8M, **μ=1.0M
Ionic strength (μ) was varied by addition of suitable amounts of sodium perchlorate.

Applying steady state treatment to the complex (C₁) and knowing that [Ru(III)]_T = [Ru(III)] + [Complex C₁], the rate law could be obtained as

$$\frac{-d[\text{Fe(CN)}_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{4k_1k_2K_1[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Ru(III)}]_T}{(k_{-1}+k_2)+k_1K_1[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-]} \text{ (2)}$$

where K₁=K/[H₂O]

At low concentrations of 4-aminobutyric acid the inequality k₋₁+k₂ ≫ k₁K₁[S][OH⁻] holds good and eq (2) reduces to eq (3)

$$\frac{-d[\text{Fe(CN)}_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{4k_1k_2K_1[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Ru(III)}]_T}{k_{-1}+k_2} \text{ (3)}$$

which clearly explains the first-order kinetics with respect to 4-aminobutyric acid at lower concentrations and first-order dependence on [OH⁻] and

[Ru(III)]. At constant [OH⁻] and higher [S] the inequality k₁K₁[S][OH⁻] ≫ k₋₁+k₂ would exist resulting in a zero-order dependence on [4-aminobutyric acid] which has been observed in the present work.

At constant [OH⁻] the plot of 1/V₁ (where V₁=-d[Fe(CN)₆³⁻]/dt) against 1/[S] gave a straight line with positive intercept on 1/V₁ axis, satisfying the Michaelis-Menten type reciprocal relationship⁶ [a kinetic proof for complex formation between Ru(III) species and 4-aminobutyric acid prior to the rate determining step] and also confirming the validity of rate law (2).

Stoichiometry and product analysis: Different sets of reaction mixture containing known excess of hexacyanoferrate(III) over 4-aminobutyric acid were kept at 30° in presence of 0.01 M NaOH and 11.47 × 10⁻⁶ M Ru(III). The amount of hexacyanoferrate(III) left in all the cases were consistent with stoichiometric eq (4).

Succinic acid was identified as reaction product by chromatographic technique.

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Stability Constants of the Complexes of Substituted Salicylic Acids with Co(II) and Ni(II)

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COMPLEXES of salicylic acid and various substituted salicylic acids have been extensively studied, mostly by pH-potentiometric method. While most of these workers¹ have reported the formation

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